

Optical Switching for data centers and advanced computing systems

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Abstract: We explore optical switching to extend network programmability to the physical layer and discuss applications of a Layer-1 Software-Defined Network (SDN) in AI/HPC clusters. In this context we identify two applications for Optical Circuit Switches (OCSs): failure resilience and reconfigurable topologies for Deep Learning workloads. We present experimental results from a DGX based testbed towards improving failure resilience and a simulation analysis for efficient Deep-Learning training in AI clusters.

1. Introduction

Enterprise and hyperscale datacenters are progressively built around Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML) workloads. The advent of Deep Learning (DL) has accelerated scaling of training compute capacity, driving the required FLOPs to double approximately every 6 months, outpacing single GPU scaling rate by a factor of five [1]. To address the growth in FLOPs performance, scale-out systems interconnected with high-speed links are required to create larger GPU domains and maintain high GPU utilization. For example, the Hopper NVIDIA DGX SuperPOD reference architecture [2] brings together 1,024 H100 GPUs and can scale to tens of thousands of GPUs. In the reference SuperPOD, the compute fabric comprises more than 2,000 cables in a two-level Fat-Tree topology that extends to three-levels for larger GPU counts [2]. At this scale, the network is an integral part of the system and its characteristics reflect on overall system performance, power, cost and availability.

We explore the use of Optical Circuit Switches to respond to these challenges. An optically switched fabric offers physical layer reconfigurability (ability to rearrange network connections according to the demand, network state etc) and programmability (ability to define the network connectivity through software/integration with an SDN controller), through the re-wiring of the network and on-demand allocation of the physical connections. The OCS fabric demarcates from the rigid, fixed physical infrastructure cabling used today and enables physical topology adaptation on-the-fly. This capability substantially extends today's software-defined network infrastructures, that are programmable down to Layer 2 (L2), adding physical layer (L1) connections as a programmable resource.

Introducing programmability to L1 facilitates a multitude of new network operations but also comes with new implications regarding integration of the new functionality to the software-defined network control-plane. This paper outlines two types of applications of the L1 programmable dataplane: fabric resilience against failures [3] and reconfigurable topologies for training of DL models [3,4]. Each application is presented separately for the sake of clarity, but the functionalities involved in each concept can be combined in a single architecture.

2. Related Work

The growth of computing demand and infrastructure in the past decades has increased the need for faster and larger networks. With optical-switching offering high bandwidth communication within a low-power and low-latency envelope, many research efforts have been dedicated towards incorporating OCSs in the DC/HPC environment, as detailed in [5]. Some early proposals, like Helios [6] and C-through [7], suggested using MEMS switches to deal with elephant flows, alongside the existing electrical network that handles mice flows. Many papers have demonstrated the potential benefits of fast optical switching, with network reconfiguration time in the range of nsec to usec [8-16]. These works focus mainly on satisfying generic demand matrices, either by calculating and enforcing optical circuits based on a demand matrix or by using forwarding methods over a variable topology. However, optical switching at high speed poses a number of challenges that have to be addressed. Hardware reconfigurability can be achieved with optical space switches [17-19], tunable lasers [20], or wavelength-selective switches [21,22]. Although such components have been demonstrated successfully, they still have not reached the level of manufacturing maturity, port scalability or insertion loss and crosstalk performance required for practical deployment. From the system point of view, fast optical switching requires system wide clock synchronization [15, 23] and fast clock and data recovery [16]. To simplify deployment, [24] proposed the use “slow” optical switches to steer the bandwidth according to the traffic requirements. Recent work from Google [25, 26], highlighted the benefits of replacing the higher layers of a Fat-Tree with OCSs and demonstrated deployment in production DCs, an important milestone towards the wider adoption of OCSs. The latest publications [27-29], examine the use of OCS in systems targeting ML applications. Most notably, [28] presents a Torus-based architecture that can be reconfigured to a twisted-Torus to better fit the traffic pattern of the applications.

3. Introducing Optical Switching into AI/HPC network fabrics

We investigate the system-level benefits of adding OCSs [30-32] to the network of advanced computing systems, focusing on AI clusters, where (full bisection) Fat-Trees (FT) are typically the reference choice for the network architecture. The introduction of optical switching in the fabric can enable, when accompanied by respective extensions to the control plane, a programmable L1 dataplane that allows on-demand re-configuration of the physical topology.

We outline two key applications that leverage the L1 programmability: i) failure resilience and ii) reconfigurable topologies for efficient DL training. Apart from the core functionality of the L1 programmable network in these applications, OCS introduction comes with the additional benefits of physical layer isolation and incremental cluster expansion. Most of the work and demonstrations presented here are focusing on the East-West part of the network (IB), though most of the described principles can be applied in other networks (Ethernet, NVLINK) as well. Fig. 1 illustrates the main integration points of optical switches in a generic 3-level FT topology.

Fig. 1. Main integration points of optical switching devices in a Fat-Tree network

The OCSs can be either augmented with the existing networking infrastructure or used to build lean networks. In the first integration scheme, the OCSs intercept the fiber connections of the reference network. The investment cost of the system increases but the benefits of topology reconfiguration can be exploited while always being able to revert to the legacy topology. For example, addition of an OCS layer between the Leaf and Spine layers of a 3-level FT (“Spine OCS layer”), as shown in Fig. 2 (a), maintains the full FT topology, since the OCSs intercept the fibers that connect the Leaf switches with the Spine switches. The Spine OCSs can be used to isolate parts of the POD, provide resiliency with redundant Spine switches and change the topology above the Leaf switches. If needed, the OCSs may just replicate the reference FT connections. In the second integration scheme, demonstrated in Fig. 2 (b), the OCSs are used to build a lean fabric by replacing the Core and Spine switches of a 3-level FT with a layer of OCSs, the “OCSs Spine layer”. In this case, the reconfigurable topologies offer reduced power, cost, HW and latency. In addition, overall network availability can improve, as the total number of components in the network is reduced and OCS failure rates are expected to be sufficiently low. The performance of the network depends on its capability to support the required traffic patterns. In this context, the system designer must take into account the targeted workloads and traffic patterns that need to be supported.

Fig. 2. a) introducing an optical switching layer (OCS Spines) between the Leaf & Spine switches, b) replacing the Spine & Core switching layers with a layer of optical switches

4. Extending SDN to Layer-1 of the network

So far, network deployments have been deeply programmable only down to L2, with SDN controllers offering almost no support for programmability on the physical cabling

infrastructure, that has been typically considered fixed after deployment. A notable exception is Google's Orion [33] SDN control plane that offers support for OCS, as part of Jupiter's DC fabric [25]. The incorporation of OCSs to the fabric enables network reconfiguration either on failures, or according to the workload/traffic-pattern changes, but this functionality introduces a new set of challenges to the network control plane. OCS-enabled networks require control plane extensions that can allocate and configure the appropriate circuits, which accommodate the connectivity requirements of the concurrently executing cluster workloads at any given time. To this end, extending the SDN control capabilities to manage L1 resources, is effectively transforming network cabling to a programmable component, that enables the runtime reconfiguration of the physical topology.

The minimum features that need to be supported by a L1 SDN controller fall within the following broad categories; modelling of the network's physical layer connectivity (switches, cables, OCSs etc), monitoring of the network elements' state/health, integration with L2 SDN controllers, interoperability with multi-vendor OCS control planes, efficient scaling to thousands of network nodes and low-latency operation. Moreover, depending on the functionality scenarios to be implemented in an OCS-enabled cluster, the feature portfolio of the L1 SDN needs to be enriched with mechanisms for fault detection and recovery to support HW resiliency, or extensions for job traffic pattern mappings to topology as well as topology-aware job placement.

Within this context we investigate a prototype control plane software extension [3] that serves as a L1 SDN controller which is responsible for the physical topology management that is carried out by driving the deployed OCS devices. This software employs a graph-based [34] data model of the physical network that includes the optical switching elements (which are transparent to all layers above L1). We introduce new concepts and algorithms that enable the described SDN L1 controller to explore and evaluate the alternative topologies of a given deployment, reconfigure the topology, and appropriately feed higher layers with enough information to react to the performed L1 changes. The software is used in the demonstration of Section 4.1.

5. Optically-enabled failure resilience

5.1 Resilience using Large OCS matrices

Multi-node AI/HPC applications rely heavily on large networks and are highly susceptible to crashing when network elements fail. In the case of large systems, switches or transceivers can fail from every 3 to every 120 hours [35], resulting in significant system impact that reduces revenues due to the unavailability of the system until the next maintenance event. The Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) of systems with tens of thousands of endpoints will be measured in minutes. The common policy of rolling back to the latest checkpoint exacerbates the loss as it discards all computations performed after the checkpoint.

Recovery of failures in large system networks currently focuses on L3 support i.e. adapting the routing configuration to exclude the failed paths where possible, since there is little or no ability to change the actual physical connectivity in real time. These approaches come with two major limitations. Firstly, they can be used only when alternative paths exist: some types of failures cannot be mitigated, e.g. Leaf switch failures that result in disconnecting the servers from the network. Secondly, this approach cannot recover the full performance of the cluster in real time since the use of alternative paths often leads to oversubscription and hence reduced performance. Multihoming can resolve this by replicating (part of) the network, e.g. connecting a server to two switches, but requires more hardware and increases deployment/operating costs.

We leverage the L1 programmable dataplane to showcase real-time recovery in an efficient, automated and software-defined manner, with minimal addition of redundant hardware. In this

context, we exploit optical switching technology to dynamically reconfigure the network connections and make failure recovery at full capacity an automated process. The hardware resilience solution relies on the addition of OCSs between the switching layers (hosts-to-Leaves, Leaves-to-Spines, Spines-to-Cores), as depicted in Fig. 3 (a), that dynamically rewire the network on demand. To offer resilience against switch failures, redundant network switches are added to the network. The redundant switches are connected to available ports of the OCSs, similarly to the regular switches. When a device failure is detected, the corresponding OCSs are properly configured to disconnect it from the network and replace it with a redundant unit.

The number of redundant switches defines a customizable level of resilience in the network, i.e., the number of failures that can be recovered simultaneously, which can vary depending on the system requirements. With the same approach, servers or even entire racks can be replaced by redundant ones in the case of unavailability (failures, updates, upgrades etc.). Fig. 3 (b) illustrates the control-plane steps for recovery in case of switch failures [3].

Fig. 3. a) optically-enabled switch resilience via the addition of OCSs, and redundant electrical switches, b) control-plane steps for recovery in case of switch failures

In order to demonstrate hardware resilience over an L1 programmable dataplane we deployed a small-scale DL testbed, that is depicted in Fig. 4 (a). The setup consists of 4 NVIDIA DGX A100 servers and 14 IB Quantum switches, connected as 8 Leaves, 4 Spines, 1 redundant Leaf (RL) and 1 redundant Spine (RS). The servers and switches were populated with 114 CWDM 200 Gb/s transceivers. A single commercial OCS [30] was partitioned to serve both server-to-leaf and leaf-to-spine connections.

The OCS is controlled by a custom L1 control plane software that serves as an SDN stack extension for physical layer resources. The L1 control plane calculates the target topology of the cluster, enforces the configuration to the physical layer devices and notifies the L2 SDN controller (IB Subnet Manager) of the changes. This enablement facilitates automatic failover switching to the redundant equipment as well as additional functionalities, such as predictive maintenance and scheduled rollout of software and hardware upgrades.

We orchestrate IB switch failures and trigger the L1 SDN control plane to initiate the failure mitigation process. Fig. 4 (b) shows the results of our tests with NCCL [36] collective communications library. The telemetry measurements show the bandwidth of the IB interfaces of a DGX server over time, for an all-reduce benchmark. Leaf switch failures would normally result in an application crash and the IB interface going offline until the failure is fixed. In case of Spine failures, the application would not crash given the availability of alternative paths, but the system would work at reduced capacity. When the resilience functionality is enabled, the full performance of the cluster is restored, in both cases, within a few seconds. We have tested the setup with UCX [37] and NCCL microbenchmarks, as well as real-world applications (MLPerf BERT, ResNet-50 and NeMo Megatron) and achieved the same performance.

Fig. 4. a) Resilience architecture and experimental setup. b) Bandwidth recovery demonstration with NCCL all-reduce. Telemetry data of Tx (yellow) and Rx (purple) bandwidth over time.

5.2 Resilience on the NIC side with 1x2 optical selectors

We examine the use of low radix $1 \times N$ optical switches for transceiver resilience. The small optical switches (a.k.a optical selectors) can be interleaved between the server NIC port pluggables and the switch uplinks via an appropriately designed connector assembly. The intent is to use selected NIC ports as backups that are not actively connected to uplinks, but only engaged at runtime when a counterpart port fails. This way the replication of ports for the server-side resilience is contained on the server side and does not require the uplink switch to feature extra ports for backup, which is particularly important when the switch radix is factored in the cluster topology design and can directly affect its scalability.

We built an experimental setup based on an optical-selector and a dual-port NIC. We placed a 1x2 optical selector in front of the NIC pluggables and deployed it in a server connecting it to a single switch port uplink. We prototype appropriate NIC firmware support by extending the existing monitoring subsystem capabilities, so that it can now react to observed port failures by driving the external optical selector to engage the other port. If a successful link bringup is detected and thus the failure is mitigated, the device driver is notified so it can proceed to resume normal operation. We have measured that a link failure event is typically mitigated within 4 seconds on NVIDIA CX6 NICs 100G Ethernet ports (Table 1), and most of this time is consumed by link bring up. Given that link bring up can significantly vary between transceiver generations, it becomes an important requirement for the proposed resilience approach. On our experimental setup the applications experience a minor glitch in performance, and resume normal operation, since reliable transports (in our case TCP) are designed to withstand such ephemeral network disruptions.

Table 1: Application recovery time for different lane speeds

Link Speed	Application level Recovery Time
100Gb/sec	4 secs
50Gb/sec	3 secs
10Gb/sec	1 sec

Our prototype has been tested with OpenVswitch [38] setups where port sources and destinations for the active rules are appropriately amended after firmware port change notification, and we also implemented a solution that works for RDMA connections and depends on the Mellanox Driver link aggregation group (LAG) support [39].

Fig. 5. Architectural blueprint of optically-enabled transceiver resilience for dual port NICs

6. Deep Learning training with OCS

The second application we explored for the L1 programmable data plane is training in DL clusters. A multi-level FT network topology based on electrical packet switches is usually employed to interconnect all the nodes in the cluster at full bisection bandwidth. The energy consumption and cost of the FT network account for a considerable portion of the total system power and cost, which is increasing with every speed upgrade. We investigate leaner network fabrics and reconfigurable topologies that fit to the communication needs of the applications. Firstly, connections across jobs are not needed; in fact, job isolation is advantageous as it mitigates cross-job interference and improves security. In addition, each DL job follows well-defined traffic patterns implemented through communication collectives. Combining the OCSs with the current FT infrastructure to leverage the advantages of both approaches is another possibility as described in section 2.

In the following subsections we present a short analysis of two options for introducing OCSs at different parts of the network: a) OCSs at the core layer – “Optical Cores”, and b) OCSs at the Spine layer – “Optical Spines”. The following paragraphs are focused on the EW network (IB/Ethernet).

6.1 Replacing the Core switching layer with OCS

The requirements and constraints related to OCS enabled networks become more stringent as we replace more layers of electrical switches, as also described in [5]. To this end, integrating the OCSs at the top of the fabric, i.e., Core/Super-Spine layer as shown in Fig. 6, emerges as a first promising step towards reaping the benefits of optical switching in the network. More pronounced energy, cost and latency savings are achievable when the OCS and control-plane technologies reach the increased maturity/performance levels required for introducing optical switching in lower layers of the topology. Replacement of the highest layer of electrical switches in a Fat Tree with OCSs, essentially transforms the topology into a reconfigurable DF+ [40] and allows programmable allocation of the inter-group links. Operational benefits of this concept like incremental deployment are mentioned in [25], with the *Optical-Cores* design offering support for tailoring topology to specific traffic patterns, as well as isolation for parts of the network for different tenants/applications.

Fig. 6. Replacement of the Core/Super-spine switching layer on a Fat-tree network with optical switches.

6.2 Lean network based on OCSs: Adding an OCS Spine Layer

The following analysis focuses on prominent examples of DL, such as large language models (LLMs) and deep learning recommendation systems (DLRMs), with exceptionally promising applications and transformational impact to society. We examine a network fabric that replaces higher layers of the FT topology with an OCS layer and study how LLM (3D Megatron) and DLRM jobs can be served over this L1 programmable data plane aiming minimum impact on cluster efficiency, yet saving network latency, energy (estimated up to 50%) and cost (estimated up to 30%).

The underlying principle of operation leverages the programmable data plane to adjust the network topology according to the expected communication pattern for each job [28,29]. Our approach assumes knowledge of basic information on the jobs arriving to the cluster, such as the collectives and parallelization approach followed. For each job and allocation of ranks, the programmable data plane implements a suitable topology (e.g. torus, full graph etc.) that aims to provide full bandwidth for the expected traffic pattern. We have studied heuristics for resource management targeting LLM (3D Megatron) and DLRM jobs. For the current work, we rely on NVIDIA DGX servers, with multiple GPUs on each server interconnected through

Fig. 7. Flat, reconfigurable network using OCSs

NVLink, along with separate connections to the programmable data plane through InfiniBand DPUs. The result is the architecture presented in Fig 7: a flat, low cost, low power and low latency network providing PHY isolation for security and performance guarantees.

As depicted in Fig. 7, DGX hosts (each with 8 GPU and 8 IB interfaces) are connected to Leaf IB switches (each with 64 IB ports, 32 towards the hosts and 32 towards the OCSs) that are subsequently connected through the OCS layer. The Spine and Core InfiniBand switches (of a 3-level Fat Tree) are replaced by OCSs that create optical circuits among the Leaf IB switches. It should be noted that the architecture of Fig. 7 is rail optimized, following the design principles of the SuperPod [2]. In the current analysis we explore how we can leverage the predictable communication collectives present in DL training.

An example of adapting the topology to job requirements is given in Fig. 8 (a). A job arrives requiring 1024 GPUs (i.e. 128 DGXs) and exhibiting an all-to-all (e.g. DLRM) pattern among them. For ease of presentation, the example allocates the 128 nodes under fully populated Leaf switches. In this case, the optimal topology is a full graph (per rail): equal distribution of connections from every Leaf to all the other Leaf switches that are part of this job. By reconfiguring the topology to a full graph, we provide full bandwidth for the all-to-all traffic pattern and ensure low latency (since there are at most 2-hops). The reductions required by DLRM jobs can also be realized over this fabric.

We extend the same principle to LLM jobs that use 3D parallelism, assuming that the tasks are accompanied by a set of parallelism parameters. We consider jobs requiring different numbers of GPUs and different combinations of tensor, data and pipeline parallelism. For the described study, tensor parallel communication is assumed to be served by the NVLink fabric, whereas data and pipeline parallel communication is served by the programmable data plane. We apply our resource management tool to adjust the network topology into a torus interconnecting the utilized GPU servers to match the network traffic pattern. Pipeline parallel communication imposes point-to-point communications among neighbors while Data parallel communication requires reductions. These traffic patterns can be served with rings that connect the involved Leaf switches in a ring topology, as shown in Fig. 8 (b). By assigning the ranks (which determine the GPUs that belong to each communication group) on the Leaf switches properly, full bandwidth can be achieved using the optical circuits.

Fig. 8. Reconfiguring the topology according to the traffic pattern: a) full graph and b) a large Torus

6.2.1 Simulation analysis for AI clusters with L1 reconfigurable fabric

To evaluate the performance of an OCS-enabled architecture under diverse topology and workload configurations we have developed a discrete event simulator that serves as the main

tool for evaluating job placement and link allocation algorithms. The simulator is composed of different functionality classes; scheduling, workload translation, resource allocation, metrics collection etc, with every class containing the respective algorithms that were developed for each functional procedure. Following the initialization stage, where the cluster model is built-up, the simulator parses a job trace file representing workloads that need to be scheduled in the cluster and subsequently performs the operations described above (scheduling, resource allocation etc.). Upon completion of the simulation run, the simulator reports the system utilization results, in conjunction with other relevant metrics that have been collected. We examine LLMs with 3D parallelism and DLRMs in a DGX based rail-optimized system with OCSs providing direct connections between the Leaf switches of the system. For the workloads of interest, the system-under-test can allocate full bandwidth for all the involved communicators, and as a result the execution time of such workloads remains the same as in commodity clusters with ideal Fat-Tree topologies. At the cluster-level, we investigate whether our strategies result in stranded resources leading to reduced cluster utilization. We define cluster utilization as the ratio of average number of servers used over the total number of servers in the system, for a time window under evaluation. Essentially, reduced cluster utilization can be translated to increased running time for the set of jobs under test. In this context, we employ our simulator to evaluate the cluster’s performance in terms of utilization over a period of time, compare it against Fat-Tree clusters and identify, via extensive metrics collection, areas for improvement in the developed algorithms. Note that the effects of reduced latency achieved through reducing switching layers, and thus network hops, are not considered. The potential benefits in the job execution time for latency sensitive workloads are under investigation.

Fig. 9 illustrates a comparative analysis, in terms of cluster utilization over time, between an OCS-enabled cluster with 32K GPU nodes against a cluster with ideal Fat-Tree fabric. Regarding the network equipment parameters, the OCS radix was considered to be 256x256 and the electrical switch radix was 64-ports with 1:1 (downlink:uplink) ratio. Both systems are evaluated using job traces that include 10,000 jobs, either LLM-only, DLRM-only or a mix of DLRM and LLM jobs. The job traces were synthetically generated with the job size uniformly

Fig. 7. Cluster utilization results comparing a 32K GPU OCS-enabled cluster against a FT-based cluster for 10,000 DLRM, LLM and 50/50 DLRM/LLM jobs. The job size for all jobs is between 64-2048 (powers-of-2) GPUs. distributed between 64-1024 (steps of 64) GPUs for DLRM jobs and between 64-2048 (steps of 64) GPUs for LLM jobs (all jobs require power-of-2 nodes). We show that the system utilization remains well within 1% of the reference FT based system for DLRMs, LLMs as well as for their mix.

7. OCS technology and ecosystem

OCS systems are now being deployed in volume in datacenters and AI systems [25]. The capability to reconfigure the network topology becomes valuable as the system scales in size and complexity. However, OCS technology is still relatively immature and bespoke, and needs continued investment to drive down cost/port, improve insertion loss, reliability and uptime. Fostering the ecosystem around OCS technology can fill current gaps and accelerate OCS adoption.

OCS insertion loss consumes a large fraction of the link budget available in typical data center optical links. Parallel single mode (PSM) transceivers used in links as long as 500 m typically allow a 3 dB link budget, whereas standard CWDM transceivers provide an extra dB to reach 2 km. Transceivers that support extended link budgets up to 6dB can and are utilized, but come at the expense of increased cost and energy consumption.

The close interplay between OCS and transceivers is underpinned by the benefit of Wavelength Division Multiplexing technology in OCS network design. WDM bundles multiple transceiver lanes into a single fiber pair allowing 4-lane interfaces to be switched via a single OCS port, effectively increasing the OCS radix and reducing the effective cost per port. Moving from PSM4 to CWDM4 transceivers improves the radix and cost/port by a factor of four. However, the decision to use WDM comes with compromises in AI network fabrics; while more wavelengths reduce the total number of OCS ports required, it also reduces the fiber fanout that can be achieved and thus, in some cases the overall network radix or size. Bidirectional fiber transmission can bring a 2x improvement in OCS port utilization but compromises full-bandwidth any-to-any connectivity across the OCS data plane.

OCS cost is expected to follow a cost-reduction curve typical for new hardware system technologies. Rising volumes can drive down the cost/port, and thus facilitate broader adoption. Integrated, “solid-state” OCS technologies bring the promise of more disruptive cost savings, especially for use cases that can accommodate a moderate number of ports. To cope with the higher loss of integrated OCS, on-chip gain should be considered, leveraging recent advancements in photonic integration platforms. Amplified OCSs can mitigate the limited link budget of standard transceivers, but this advantage comes at the expense of a more sophisticated link design to factor in amplifier noise and nonlinearities.

AI systems exhibit exceptional complexity, hence successful addition of OCS as a new component necessitates extremely high reliability. Although OCSs can improve network availability through resource redundancy (section 4), an OCS failure could still affect multiple network ports. It is important to optimize reliability of all building blocks within the OCS spanning from the optics to the electronic drivers, the digital control logic, the power supply units and fans etc. Insights from reliability modelling can feed back to system design, optimizing parameters such as OCS radix, blast radius and system partitioning, and adding component redundancy or field replaceability to reduce downtime.

8. Conclusion

Optical switching extends SDN programmability to the physical layer. The programmable data plane enables new functionalities that can sustain growth in scale-out systems. We demonstrated real-time failover to redundant IB switches, successfully restoring the full performance of the cluster to improve availability. We also explored flat architectures for LLM and DLRM training, optimizing the topology to the traffic pattern. Continued investment in OCS technologies is essential to lower costs, reduce insertion loss, and further enhance the reliability of optical circuit switches, thereby accelerating their adoption.

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